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Beef Cattle Development Policy at Food Crop Producer Centers: Case Study in Gorontalo Regency

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Abstract

This study aimed to prioritize alternative policies and allocate resources for beef cattle development. It was conducted in Gorontalo Regency, from January to April 2019. The survey method was used to collect data and solve problems. Secondary data sourced from related institutions and primary data from livestock stakeholders. Respondents were determined through judgment sampling techniques, such as people who understand the problems of developing beef cattle. Secondary data collected through documentation, while primary data through observation, interviews, and questionnaires using the Saaty Scale. Data analysis uses the Analytic Hierarchy Process method. The results showed that alternative priorities of beef cattle development policies that could be implemented were: 1) improvement of feed logistics facilities (0.291), 2) integration of beef cattle with rice and maize (0.272), 3) institutional strengthening of farmers (0.146), 4) increase in farmer's capacity (0.101), 5) introduction of feed processing technology (0.097), 6) coordination between policymakers (0.053), and 7) increase cooperation with partner institutions (0.039). The accumulated value of the percentage increase in feed logistics facilities and integration of beef cattle with rice and maize was by 56.3%. More than 50% of resources can be allocated to support the implementation of alternative policies through 1) the construction of mini feed mills and barns at the farmer group or village level, and 2) the development of a system of integration of rice with beef cattle and integration of maize with beef cattle.

Keywords: Policy, Beef Cattle, Food Crops, System Integration

INTRODUCTION

Gorontalo Regency is one of the locations of developing agricultural areas with superior commodities developed, namely rice, maize and beef cattle. The development of beef cattle in this region is supported by the potential of feed resources, both natural forage and agricultural food crop waste. This situation is supported by the commitment of the Gorontalo Regency Government, who wants to make livestock as its main subsector.

Gorontalo Regency Government through the livestock service desires to make this area as one of the centers of beef cattle producers in eastern Indonesia. This is to be realized with the hope of being able to supply other regions in Sulawesi and Kalimantan, such as North Sulawesi, North Kalimantan and East Kalimantan.

The development of beef cattle in the Gorontalo Regency has been carried out for a long time, but it is still not as expected even though various policies and programs have been launched by the central and regional governments. In 2002 - 2003 the government launched the Rice - Livestock System Integration Program and in 2005 - 2014 launched the Beef Self-Sufficiency Program. The reality in the farming community, the policies and programs have not been able to encourage farmers to utilize the potential of existing food resources to increase beef cattle population and production.

Problems in the development of beef cattle originated from the development that still relies on traditional folk farms. Farmers carry out traditional beef cattle cultivation and have not considered optimizing production. The livestock business is still a side business or just a spare time in between agricultural activities and has not

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been used as a commercial business. The traditional beef cattle business is also characterized by the lack of management applications and cultivation technology, including in the supply of feed so that the development of livestock with high population growth is difficult to achieve.

Livestock population can be increased through the provision of good food; therefore, it is necessary to change the traditional food supply system that only relies on natural forage to use food crop waste as animal feed. Gorontalo Regency is a center of food crop producers, especially rice and maize whose waste is still abundant, so research studies are aimed at prioritizing alternative policies and allocating resources for beef cattle development in Gorontalo Regency.

METHOD

Place and time of research

This research was conducted in the administrative area of Gorontalo Regency. The research location was determined purposively by considering the potential possessed, there are: 1) the location of agricultural development for beef cattle, rice and maize (Permentan No. 50 of 2012), 2) the largest beef cattle population in Gorontalo Province which reached 37% (BPS Kabupaten Gorontalo, 2018), 3) centers of food crop producers that produce rice and maize waste for beef cattle feed. This research was conducted for three months, from January to April 2019.

Research methods

Survey research methods are used to collect data and solve problems. Data is displayed in the form of numbers, tables and graphs. Secondary data from related institutions in the form of regional regulations, regional spatial plans and strategic plans sourced. Primary data sourced from livestock stakeholders, namely: officials, policymakers, professionals, and practitioners of beef cattle farms.

Respondents were determined through judgment sampling techniques, such as people who are experienced and understand the problems of developing beef cattle in Gorontalo Regency. Selected respondents represented livestock stakeholders from several institutions related to beef cattle development. Respondents were 9 people with composition, they were: livestock and animal health service (head of department, head of division, section head, and head of technical implementation unit) 4 people, regional people's representative council 1 person, animal husbandry study program 2 people, beef cattle farmers association 1 person, and 1 group of beef cattle farmers.

Secondary data is collected through the documentation process, while primary data is collected through observation, interviews, and structured questionnaires. Interviews with respondents were conducted to explore all existing problems as well as formulate alternative policies that could be a solution to the problem of beef cattle development. The questionnaire distributed to respondents was a closed list of questions using the Saaty Scale.

Data analysis

Integrative policy analysis is used to formulate alternative beef cattle development policies at centers of food crop producers that can be implemented in the Gorontalo Regency. The analysis was performed using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. This method begins by creating criteria for problems based on the perspectives or perspectives of representative expert respondents, namely: policymakers, professionals, and experienced animal husbandry practitioners.

The combination of methods' triangulation and data sources is used to study interconnected problems from different perspectives so that the validity of the data can be maintained. The triangulation process is carried out by comparing and exploring data truths through several data collection techniques, namely interviews, observations, and documentation, both written documents and drawings until the data is saturated and complete.

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Based on the triangulation process, it is known that there are various problems faced in developing beef cattle in the centers of food crop producers. The existing problems are then analyzed using the AHP method. The analysis begins with the decomposition of problems to break down existing problems into elements and group them into complex hierarchical structures. The hierarchy structure of beef cattle development illustrates the problems in groups and levels. The problem decomposition process produces several levels of the hierarchy, namely: level 1 (goal), level 2 (criteria), level 3 (sub-criteria), and level 4 (alternative).

Based on the hierarchy structure of beef cattle development, an assessment is carried out through pairwise comparison of the elements of criteria, sub-criteria and alternative policies so that the weighting of each element's value is known. The assessment of two elements at a certain level related to the level above is done based on the Saaty Scale, as the following table.

The fundamental scale of the absolute numbers table

Intensity of Importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective
2	Weak or slight	
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment slightly favor one activity over another
4	Moderate plus	
5	Strong importance	Experience and judgment strongly favor one activity over another
6	Strong plus	
7	Very strong	An activity is favored very strongly over another, its dominance demonstrated in practice
8	Very, very strong	
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favoring one activity over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation
Reciprocals	If activity <i>i</i> has one of the above non-zero numbers assigned to it when compared with activity <i>j</i> , then <i>j</i> has the reciprocal value when compared with <i>i</i>	A reasonable assumption

Source: Saaty, 2008

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hierarchy structure of beef cattle development

The development of beef cattle is often accompanied by a variety of problems that can hinder the achievement of its objectives. Based on the triangulation process, it is known that there are various problems faced in the development of beef cattle. Existing problems require resolution through decision making by decision-makers. Fanani (2017) states that decision making consists of several stages, which named: 1) defining the problem clearly, 2) compiling a list of problems so that there is systematic orientation, 3) identifying the problem to provide a more specific picture, 4) mapping problems based on the group by using models or test equipment.

Mapping the problem using the AHP method is done through the decomposition process. Various problems related to the development of beef cattle in the centers of food crop producers are broken down and grouped in the form of a hierarchical structure. Retnoningsih (2015) states that decision-makers must break problems into elements and arrange them in a complex hierarchical structure.

The arrangement of the hierarchy depends on imagination, experience, and knowledge also depends on logic to give various considerations so that it is in accordance with intuitive estimates (Bourgeois, 2005). This process is determined by the actors or policymakers by paying attention to solving the problem or desired solution in the form of alternative beef cattle development policies at centers of food crop producers.

The hierarchical structure is a picture of the relationship of problems in groups and stratified based on factual reality and the perspective of respondents. Problem decomposition produces several levels of a hierarchical structure, namely: goals, criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives. Goal development of beef cattle in centers of food crop producers is broken down into three criteria, namely: 1) the state of beef cattle development areas, 2) the real conditions of beef cattle farms, and 3) government policy support.

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The situation of beef cattle development areas is broken down into several sub-criteria, such as 1) the state of the ecological environment, 2) the state of the socio-economic and cultural environment of farmers, 3) the distribution of livestock commodities, and 4) the availability of livestock feed resources. The real conditions of beef cattle farms include several sub-criteria, such as 1) livestock population conditions, 2) livestock farming systems, 3) livestock businesses, and 4) beef cattle farmer capacity. Government policy support is broken down into several sub-criteria, such as 1) policymakers, 2) substance of policy products, 3) institutional beef cattle farmers, and 4) collaboration with supporting partner institutions.

The triangulation process for the solution to the problem of developing beef cattle in the centers of food crop producers produces several alternative policies, which named: 1) integration of beef cattle with rice and maize, 2) improvement of feed logistics facilities, 3) introduction of feed processing technology, 4) increasing the capacity of farmers' knowledge and skills, 5) coordination between policymakers, 6) strengthening farmers' institutions, and 7) increasing cooperation with supporting partner institutions.

Alternative priorities for beef cattle development policies

The weight value of each element at each level affects the priority of elements in the hierarchical structure. The results of the assessment of each element at each level, from the goal to the sub-criteria are presented in Figure 1. Alternative priorities for beef cattle development policies that will be implemented are known after the synthesis of priorities for all assessment results.

The first assessment was carried out on the element of problem criteria related to beef cattle development goals in the centers of food crop producers. The calculation results show that the element of government policy support (0.564) has a higher weighting value than the real conditions of beef cattle ranching (0.294) and the state of beef cattle development areas (0.142). Government policy support is the most important element and occupies the highest priority in the development of beef cattle in Gorontalo Regency.

Beef cattle development will run well if supported by policy instruments made by policymakers, namely policies with substance that can solve farmers' problems. Dwidjowijoto (2003) stated that policymakers are policy actors who determine policy formulation and have the authority to determine the substance and legitimacy of policies. Representative institutions of the people (legislative) and the government (executive) are policy-making institutions. Therefore the Gorontalo Regency People's Representative Council as the legislative and Gorontalo Regency Animal Husbandry Department as executives must be able to formulate policies that can be a solution to farmers' problems.

Figure 1. The Beef cattle development hierarchy structure outline

The next stage of the assessment is carried out on the sub-criteria element related to the criteria of the problem. Evaluation on the sub-criteria element related to the condition criteria of the beef cattle development area shows that the element of the availability of livestock feed resources (0.074) has a higher value weight than the ecological environment (0.026), the socio-economic and cultural environmental conditions (0.026), and the distribution of livestock commodities (0.017). These results indicate that the problem of availability of feed occupies the highest priority to be solved in the problem of the state of beef cattle development areas.

Beef cattle development is very dependent on the availability of feed because feed is a major component for the life, growth, production and reproduction of livestock. The feed is a very important factor of production because, in the composition of production costs, more than 70% of the costs incurred by farmers are feed costs (DG PKH, 2011). Beef cattle business will be profitable if farmers are continuously able to provide quality feed as needed at a low cost.

Evaluation on the sub-criteria element related to the criteria of the real condition of beef cattle farming shows that the element of beef cattle farmer capacity (0.145) has a higher weighting value than the livestock farming system (0.071), livestock business (0.055), and livestock population conditions (0.024). These results indicate that improving the knowledge and skills of farmers must be prioritized in solving the real conditions of beef cattle farms.

Problems that hinder the development of beef cattle, such as the assumption that beef cattle can find their own food, causes farmers to be less serious in providing quality feed and adequate feed means to support the optimization of livestock production and reproduction. The ability of farmers to adopt research results on management and feed technology is still very low so that the results of research on improving the quality of feed that has been sought by various research institutions have not been widely used. This situation is caused by limited knowledge and skills, time, and business capital owned by farmers.

Various problems develop beef cattle, but they all start from the traditional pattern of raising cattle. (Suhubdy, 2007) states that the traditional mindset about providing food is a big challenge in developing beef cattle. Farmers assume that beef cattle must get a fresh feed that is still green. This is an obstacle in the utilization of agricultural food crop waste as animal feed, so efforts are needed to increase the knowledge and skills of farmers in order to be able to utilize the abundant food crop agricultural waste.

Assessments on sub-criteria elements related to government policy support criteria show that the element of institutional beef cattle farmers (0.289) has a higher value weight than the substance of policy products (0.117), supporting partner institutions (0.089), and policymakers (0.068). These results indicate that related to government policy support, institutional problems of beef cattle farmers occupy the highest priority to be resolved.

Institutionalization of farmers in the community, such as breeder groups and livestock associations, is one of the determinants of the success of beef cattle development. Institutional problems of farmers occur because the number of farmers groups continues to increase, but it is not accompanied by the addition of field facilitators so that coaching does not go as expected. Evaluating old groups and coaching reaching all groups is difficult. Farmer groups with good management and receive regular guidance from field assistants will support the successful development of beef cattle.

The beef cattle breeding association, which is a forum for livestock stakeholders has not yet seen its contribution to the development of beef cattle. Livestock associations, such as the Indonesian Cattle and Buffalo Farmers Association consisting of beef cattle farmer stakeholders, can become strategic partners of the animal husbandry service so that their existence must be supported and given space to provide constructive input in the development of beef cattle.

The final assessment is carried out on alternative policies related to the sub-criteria elements. The weighted value of the synthesis results shows the alternative priorities of beef cattle development policies that can be implemented, namely: 1) improvement of feed logistics facilities (0.291), 2) integration of beef cattle with rice and maize (0.272), 3) institutional strengthening of farmers (0.146), 4) increasing the capacity of

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farmers (0.101), 5) introduction of feed processing technology (0.097), 6) coordination between policymakers (0.053), and 7) increasing cooperation with partner institutions (0.039), as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Synthesis of priority for beef cattle development

The results of the synthesis of priorities indicate that the improvement of feed logistics facilities has a higher value weight than other policy alternatives. Inconsistency values smaller than 0.1 indicate that, in general, respondents are consistent in giving their perceptions so that all assessment results are considered valid and acceptable.

Problems with providing food occur because farmers do not take into account the availability and demand in anticipating feed shortages in the long dry season (DG PKH, 2011). Guaranteed continuity of beef cattle feed availability can be done by increasing feed logistics facilities.

The results of the priority synthesis are displayed in the form of a dynamic sensitivity graph showing the percentage value of criteria and alternative policies for beef cattle development (Figure 3). The percentage of policy alternatives makes it easy for policymakers to allocate their resources to support the development of beef cattle. Criteria for government policy support have the largest percentage value. This shows that to implement alternative policies for beef cattle development requires large support from the government as a policy-making institution.

Figure 3. Dynamic sensitivity graph for beef cattle development

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The dynamic sensitivity graph display shows two policy alternatives that have the highest percentage value, namely the improvement of feed logistics facilities and the integration of beef cattle with rice and maize. The accumulated percentage value of these two policy alternatives is 56.3%, so that more than 50% of the resources owned for beef cattle development can be allocated to support the two alternative policies. Improvement of feed logistics facilities can be in the form of a program to build mini feed mills and barns from the farmer group level to the village level, and permanent pens with proper feedlot for beef cattle.

Gorontalo Regency region is very supportive of the development of beef cattle in synergy with food crop farming because it is an agricultural development area for rice, maize and beef cattle (Permentan No. 50 of 2012). This development model is known as the Crop Livestock System, both integration of beef cattle with rice and integration of beef cattle with maize.

The application of food crop integration with beef cattle has a multiplier effect or many benefits for livestock, farmers and the environment. Beef cattle get enough food from agricultural waste, farmers can increase livestock ownership and income, and environmental damage from burning agricultural waste can be avoided. Bad habits of burning agricultural waste can lead to land degradation, environmental pollution, damage to ecosystems, and loss of biodiversity.

Farmers' institutions are the actors of livestock development in the field so that it becomes one of the determinants of the success of the beef cattle development program. Institutional strengthening of farmers can be in the form of improving the system of data collection of farmers and beef cattle farm associations, routine assistance and coaching that reaches all breeder groups and evaluating the organization and development of livestock businesses that are run.

Improvement of farmers' capacity is aimed at improving livestock business performance, income, and welfare of farmers. This can be in the form of improving the knowledge and skills of farmers about beef cattle farming systems, ranging from feed management, maintenance, postharvest handling, to animal health and welfare. Improvement of farmers' knowledge and skills can be made through ongoing training and counseling.

Feed processing is one of the important components in feed management that can be implemented in feed ingredients from food crop waste, such as straw and rice bran. Rice straw contains approximately 5% protein with digestibility reaching 30-40%, so the nutritional content must be increased first before it is given to cattle through processing. Rice straw can be processed through physical, chemical and biological treatment (Achmadi, 2010). All of these treatments aim to extend the storage period and improve feed quality so as to optimize the utilization of straw and increase beef cattle productivity.

Rice straw is physically processed by chopping, grinding, soaking, boiling, and making pellets. Physical processing can increase the speed of fermentation and consumption of animal feed. Chemical rice straw processing is done using chemicals, such as ammonium and sodium. Ammonia is useful for increasing nitrogen content, digestibility, and the quantity of feed consumption. Biologically processed rice straw is done by utilizing a microbial starter. This biotechnology product can dissolve insoluble minerals thereby increasing the digestibility of dry materials of rice straw. The quality of fermented rice straw is better because the levels of crude protein have increased while the levels of crude fiber cellulose and lignin have decreased so as to increase feed digestibility and beef cattle productivity (Syamsu, 2011).

Food crop waste processing has the potential to become new jobs that can absorb labor. This activity can meet the needs of animal feed and facilitate farmers in providing feed so that there is an opportunity to increase beef cattle ownership. The utilization of food crop waste can also increase farmers' income from waste that was previously considered to be of no economic value.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description of the results and discussion, several conclusions are obtained, such as:

- 1) Alternative priorities for beef cattle development policies in Gorontalo Regency, namely: 1) improvement of feed logistics facilities, 2) integration of beef cattle with rice and maize, 3) institutional strengthening of farmers, 4) capacity building of farmers' knowledge and skills, 5) introduction of feed processing

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technology, 6) coordination between policymakers, and 7) increasing cooperation with supporting partner institutions.

- 2) Alternative policies that have the highest percentage value, namely the improvement of feed logistics facilities and integration of beef cattle with rice and maize so that resources can be allocated to support the implementation of alternative policies through programs: 1) the construction of mini feed mills and barns in farmer group or village area level, 2) the development of integration of rice with beef cattle and integration of maize with beef cattle.

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